

Title: Implementing Neural Nets in Unity

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INTRODUCTION:

Teaching developers how to implement AI in Augmented and Virtual Reality can unlock nearly unlimited potential. In fact, it is the next step in AR/VR evolution. From teaching vehicles and robots how to navigate autonomously to understanding the most efficient layout of roadways or utilities, and eventually - we can use AI in AR/VR to autonomously generate elements for our new 3D worlds that are adjusted to our location, mood, biometrics, and previous experiences.

AIM:

To provide an easily accessible means for developers to implementing and use Neural Networks in Unity3D for Augmented and Virtual Reality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A Genetic Algorithm called NeuroEvolution of Augmenting Topologies (NEAT), created by Kenneth O. Stanley, was used to train GameObjects to move from their starting point to a target location. This implementation was created in the popular game engine Unity3D. NEAT finds the best balance between structure and weights to achieve the highest fitness possible.

RESULTS:

The NEAT algorithm was able to figure out the locomotion method to get the object efficiently from point A to point B.

CONCLUSIONS:

After conducting multiple experiments and seeing varying results, I showed the final outcome to many developers and most of them said they were interested in learning how to implement these findings. This points to a large gap between developers who want to use AI in Unity3D and those that actually know how to.

KEYWORDS:

Neural Network, Artificial Intelligence, AI, Augmented Reality, AR, Virtual Reality, VR, Unity 3D, Unity3D, Game Engine, Software Developer, Engineer, NEAT, NeuroEvolution of Augmenting Topologies, Hologram, Holographic

BIOGRAPHY:

Tyler Lindell is a self-taught Software Developer who has completed his BS in Business Administration from Warner Pacific College. He is an Augmented Reality and Artificial Intelligence Software Engineer at Holographic Interfaces (A startup that builds custom AR/VR applications for companies like yours. The most well known application was for the Hyperloop team rLoop (renamed to Euroloop) while they were competing in the SpaceX Hyperloop competition. He is also a Software Engineer at Tesla.